

Short Communication

Toward A Novel Method to Address Viral Infections

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Received: July 12, 2023

Accepted: August 14, 2023

Published: August 29, 2023

Abstract: This short communication briefly presents the result of long years of general investigations on germs, particularly viral infections. Seeing the nature of viruses and how they operate, we postulate that once infected, the individual could never clear a virus thoroughly from his body systems. We propose a novel method for researchers and the scientific community to exploit to solve definitively the problem of viral infections. We explain how the human body and its vital energy emanate from the same source and open up about the obstacles we faced during our research.

Keywords: The Entangled System Degradation/Synthesis, Information, Order, Disorder, Germs, Vaccines, Lithium, Sodium-Potassium Pump.

1. Introduction

This short communication falls within the framework of quantum biology, a new tool that rescues traditional biology and helps it elucidate tough questions related to living organisms [1, 2]. From the beginning of my publications, I opened up about how achievers made their discoveries, and one of my jobs was to clarify this aspect of the scientific endeavor. We cannot be efficient in solving the problem of humanity while dwelling in ignorance; for that cause, we must understand who we are as human beings and what composes our beings. Anyone following our research and publications will realize that humans are made of immaterial components in a physical body; we are energetic beings living in physical bodies [3]. Upon entering the body at birth, the vital energy (still unknown) splits into three functional parts that operate over three principal organs: the heart, the blood, and the brain. As my research has focused on sleep, I have demonstrated the conditions upon which the vital energy remains in the body and why it departs, what we commonly call death. I amply demonstrated why we sleep, faint, and die [4, 5].

A tightly controlled balance between degradation and synthesis maintains life in the physical body [6]; unfortunately, degradation becomes refractory as we age, and the balance ruptures, leading to death. Germs are another way to accelerate the dissolution process; they increase chaos in the body. This short communication will address the second topic that occupied my time as an independent researcher. Here, I present and propose a novel method to solve virus-related problems.

2. The Same Filthy Behavior in Science: The Material World and Life Within It

The story of science is full of naysayers, and novel ideas often are met with opposition. From Ignaz Semmelweis to Dan Shechtman, scientists seem to have their own ideas about how Nature should behave, but reality says the opposite. As Michael Behe said, the job of science is to describe the world as it is, not as we want it to be. Scientists often lend their thoughts to Nature, not knowing how limited we are as human beings; we perceive less than one percent of the whole electromagnetic spectrum, and our peripheral vision is limited at a 120-degree around; therefore, too many things escape our sight. Scientists in those days had no cognizance of such a phenomenon; they killed

Doctor Semmelweis (accidentally, of course) because they could not perceive any germs in their hands.

Science has only four hundred years old, and we are still learning. We continue ferreting out secrets Nature hides in its bosom. For that cause, religious people and scientists must put some water in their wine; there are many things we don't know yet. Why is the material universe asymmetric, and why are biomolecules homochiral?

While these two questions are still puzzling researchers, the answer lies before our eyes. Most recent investigations scientists have conducted in various science disciplines yield the response, yet we are unaware of it; this simple fact shows how distracted we are. Both scientists and religious people spend time quarreling with each other, believing science and religion are antipodes; they are not. Scientists and religious people misinterpret respectively scientific data and sacred texts; that's why they oppose and fight each other. Meanwhile, religion and science are moving in the same direction. In his *Annus Mirabilis* publications, the September paper, "Does the Inertia of a Body Depend Upon Its Energy-content?" demonstrated that $E=mc^2$, meaning energy and mass are equivalent; in other words, the realm of energy yields the material universe [7]. While the immaterial realm is a perfect symmetry, the material world is not; this is so because one begets the other. As Yoichiro Nambu and Jeffrey Goldstone's research showed, a massless boson appears whenever a field of continuous symmetry experiences a spontaneous breakdown. And the work of Peter Higgs demonstrates that bosons are the precursors of the material world [8]. As the nascent Higgs field expanded, the massless particles slowed down due to the effect of entropy; they clumped together and acquired mass. Thus, the material universe is asymmetric because it was born out of a spontaneous symmetry breaking of a continuous symmetry of the energy field. Notice that the same symmetry breakdown kicks life out of the physical body [9, 10].

Energy first is manifested as material objects, a concatenation of Information, Order, and Disorder, then life emerges as subjects inside objects. With life, Order and Disorder form an entangled system, one of the fundamental characteristics of living organisms. Notice that life is ordered according to a set of Information in the same way matter is found in an ordered state. Atoms in crystals and quasicrystals follow some order because their formations are governed by Information; the only exception in material objects is that Order and disorder are not entangled; hence there is no life in crystals [11].

These statements are not mere speculations because we experiment ourselves. We toil to establish our claims as scientific facts for over twenty years, and we separate philosophy from science. How do I know that energy is made of a concatenation of Information and Order? Through revelation first, and then through testing. Science is about experiments, and I invite readers to test my claim [12]. In a dark room without windows filled with various objects, the experimenter can blindfold his son or daughter and introduce him or her to the room. Tell her to take off the cover and let her describe the room. She will be unable because her brain has no photons coming to process. She will spend the entire twenty-four hours in the middle of the room without identifying one item. Now, switch on the light and ask her to describe the room's contents. It will take a few minutes for the kid to "eido"¹ the room and name all the items. As light from the bulb shines in the room, photons convey Information to her retina, which the brain analyzes.

Energy is made of a concatenation of Information and Order; the realm of energy is perfect symmetry because electromagnetism, one of its fundamental aspects, is a continuous symmetry. Information and Order are eternally in concatenation because, without Order, Information will be useless and meaningless. For instance, the English alphabet means nothing unless arranged in a specific order; there is no information without order.

¹Eido is a Greek word that connotes awareness. As a verb it means to perceive or be sure to see.

As Einstein's formula shows, energy begets the material world, and since entropy causes space-time to be and helps clump together massless bosons into material particles, all matter is fundamentally made of Information, Order, and Disorder. That said, life is another step further in the manifestation of energy, and it expresses itself in objects. Therefore, three fundamental elements characterize all lifeforms on Earth: a boundary fence, a system of executive Information, and the entangled system degradation/synthesis (Disorder/Order). These three elements separate objects from living organisms, and the last one segregates viruses from bacteria; for that cause, viruses are not part of the Tree of Life [13, 14].

3. The Obstacles in My Way

After finishing my emergency medicine classes in 2014, I started experimenting with germs again, this time on a new level. In 2017 while I was in Baton Rouge, Louisiana, I received a revelation that I put to the test. Today, I can conclude that the formula was presented to me as a placebo because homeopathy has been debunked as a genuine scientific theory. I discussed placebo in my philosophical novel "On Love and Relationships," which unfortunately remained unpublished. I had that vision probably to help focus my attention because I was truly distracted. My detractors put a camera in my room, and I was more playful than conscientious. It is one way I was directed to get more serious about my work, and I finally reached a pellucid conclusion about viral infections.

My life as an independent researcher in science was not easy because of naysayers and detractors. While our society is filled with problems, they do nothing but stand in the way, blocking all the passage; they have all the reasons why things will not work. Some of them cannot distinguish a syndrome from a disease. A syndrome is a set of medical signs and symptoms associated with some particular disorders in the body; it disturbs homeostasis but does not lead to the collapse of the entangled system degradation/synthesis. While the varicella virus may trigger a disease in the body, its metamorphosis and reactivation into herpes zoster in later years does not generate a disease but a syndrome [15]. The activation of these final viruses is strongly correlated with sleep, especially the resting phase of the sleeping process. Notice that the transmission of a zoster virus occurs during its activation phase in the presence of a rash or blister [16]. After all, despite the obstacles, we did thrive and achieved a result with our investigations.

4. My Finding and Proposition

Howard Markel reported in chapter eleven, page 163 of his book "The Secret of Life," an unusual advice Francis Crick gave young Watson. The author narrated how Mr. Crick taught Dr. Watson that Pauling's accomplishment was a result of common sense, not complicated mathematical reasoning [17]. Sometimes, it takes common sense to solve complex problems, and our proposition to address viral infection is another example. In my investigation of the topic, contrary to popular belief, I have postulated that once infected, the host never clears a virus's genetic material thoroughly; this statement applies to almost all viruses. They either lay dormant through a lysogenic cycle, could mutate under another favorable circumstance, undergo a lytic cycle, or could be disabled for good because only a few of their material remains in the host's genetic program [15]. In any of these cases above, the host keeps a viral genetic material forever, whether in an active form or a disabled one.

Today, we know the modus operandi of almost all viruses; they operate like thieves; once they enter the cell, they incorporate their genetic materials and become a part of the host [18, 19]. What is the easiest and most efficient way to prevent a burglar from ransacking your home? The translucently clear answer is to prevent him from entering your property or make sure he does not get out when he succeeds in penetrating the facility. I will refrain from developing further because this idea alone sends professional researchers investigating viruses down a new pathway. Vaccines are helpful but are not the most efficient way to address the question definitively [16]. If we want to solve the problem of viruses, preventing them from entering the cell is the best way; therefore, one item appears critical.

The item in the revelation I received was Lithium. This chemical element is classified as an alkali metal of the same family group as Sodium and Potassium, the two principal elements I have suspected to maintain and control the electromagnetic field over cells of various organs and systems, namely the cardiovascular and central nervous systems. The work of Danish Chemist Jens C. Skou on the sodium/potassium pump won him the Nobel Prize in 1997 [20].

The first step in this novel endeavor is to study cell membranes to understand how the electromagnetic field is generated. Understanding how viruses dock to unload their genetic material is also paramount. From there, researchers could figure out how to thwart their mechanism of action and prevent them from breaching into the cell.

5. Conclusion

All living beings are made of two distinct parts that come together. The energetic part lives inside the material shell, and the game of life consists of maintaining these two parts by preventing them from flying apart. Entropy is the main culprit that causes such dissolution, and viruses appear to be dreadful agents, contributing to the increase of chaos in the body. Therefore, the genuine way to solve the issue is to prevent them from entering the cells of living organisms by strengthening the electromagnetic field over organs and systems of the body. It is a new idea, but better than the vaccines if we succeed in achieving it.

Declarations

Acknowledgments: Not applicable.

Funding: This research received no specific grant from any funding agency.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares no affiliation, hence no conflict of interest. This investigation was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships.

Ethical Approval: Not required.

Informed Consent: Not applicable.

Author Contribution: Wrote the whole paper.

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Citation: Edoh ZA. Toward A Novel Method to Address Viral Infections. *Int J Rec Innov Med Clin Res.* 2023;5(3):22-26.

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